

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Beta-catenin is an immune regulator.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Loss of function analysis demonstrated the tumor suppressor-like molecule has a dominant function in fine control of self non-self through activation of tissue-restricted antigens, most likely to restrict metastasis to distant organ sites.